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*“Integrated Agriculture, Natural Farming,
Biodiversity Conservation and Rural Bio-
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7-9 December 2021

**College of Agriculture (CAU-I)
Kyrdemkulai, Meghalaya**

Organized by:

**NAAS Regional Chapter–Barapani, Meghalaya
International Union of Organic Agriculture, Shillong and
College of Agriculture, Central Agricultural University (Imphal),
Kyrdemkulai, Meghalaya**

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Dr. U.K. Behera

Organizing Chairman

International Conference on Integrated Agriculture, Natural Farming, Biodiversity Conservation and Rural Bio-Entrepreneurship under Changing Climate Scenario Dean, College of Agriculture (CAU, Imphal), Kyrdemkulai, Ri-Bhoi, Meghalaya-793105, India

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Dr. Lala I.P. Ray, Associate Professor, CPGSAS (CAU-Imphal), Umiam-793103, Meghalaya, India.

Editors

Drs. Dibakar Mahanta, H.G. Kencharaddi, M. Premi Devi, Lala I.P. Ray and U.K. Behera

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Evaluation of different hive designing for *Apis cerana himalayana* in NEH region of India

S.M. HALDHAR, K.I. SINGH AND A. SUCHITRA DEVI

*Department of Entomology, College of Agriculture (CAU), Iroisemba, Imphal, Manipur 795004
Email: haldhar80@gmail.com*

Abstract

Asian honey bee, *Apis cerana* is a species of honeybee native to South, South East and East Asia. This species is the sister species of *Apis koschevnikovi* and both are in the same subgenus. *Apis cerana* having three subspecies in India and in which one subspecies is *Apis cerana Himalaya* that found only in NEH region of India. *A. cerana Himalaya* colonies are known for building nests consisting of multiple combs in cavities containing a small entrance, presumably for defense against invasion by individuals of another nest. Moreover, *A. cerana Himalaya* is known for its highly social behavior, reflective of its classification as a type of honey bee. We found from different hive designing experiment that ISI A type

with 8 frames has the maximum egg laying area of (300.33 cm²), brood area of (1261 cm²), honey store of (528.33 cm²) pollen stores of (521.00 cm²) followed by local made hive with (268 cm²), (1235 cm²), (500.33 cm²) and (490.33 cm²) of egg laying area, brood area, honey store and pollen store respectively and the least was found in Modified ISI A type hive with brood chamber and frame reduced by 2 inch with 6 frames. This shows that ISI A type with 8 frames is a scientific and most advance hive for *A. cerana himalayana*. It is recommended that the use of ISI A type hive followed local made hive best for *A. cerana himalayana* in NEH region.

Keywords: *Apis cerana Himalaya*, hive designing, NEH region.